

Reproducibility analysis of a research paper: "User-controllable Recommendation Against Filter Bubbles"

KRISTIAN RISTIC, Technische Universität Wien, Austria

JOAN SALVÀ, Technische Universität Wien, Austria

IVA PEZO, Technische Universität Wien, Austria

WILLIAM AMMINGER, Technische Universität Wien, Austria

In this project we reproduce the experimental setup, experiments, and results as explained in the scientific paper "User-controllable Recommendation Against Filter Bubbles". The task of interest is to confirm the numbers and findings reported in the paper or, alternatively, uncover inconsistencies and challenge the conclusions drawn.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproducibility, Experiment Design, Filter Bubbles, Recommendation Systems

1 THE SCIENTIFIC PAPER

1.1 Investigation of three papers

The initial 3 papers chosen that suited our interest were:

- Clicks can be Cheating: Counterfactual Recommendation for Mitigating Clickbait Issue
- Task-Oriented Dialogue System as Natural Language Generation
- User-controllable Recommendation Against Filter Bubbles

When deciding which paper to proceed with, a primary factor was the amount of project resources readily available to reproduce the experiment. For example the language generation paper had no reference to its source code or data-sets used online. Therefore the exact methodology of the paper would be quite cumbersome to reproduce. The filter bubble paper was selected in the end due to the availability of the source code, along with it presenting an interesting topic.

1.2 Motivation, proposal and research questions

Recommender systems become increasingly important to provide personalized information. A standard recommender systems is mining user interest from user features (e.g., gender and age) and historical interactions (e.g., click). Due to merely fitting the data, recommender systems typically face filter bubble issues: continually recommending many homogeneous items, isolating users from diverse contents. Moreover, due to the feedback loop of such models, filter bubbles can gradually become severer.

There are many approaches on how to mitigate filter bubbles, but this paper argues that users should have the power to decide whether to mitigate filter bubbles and choose which bubble to mitigate.

The researchers propose a User-Controllable Inference (UCI) framework that incorporates:

- User-feature controls at two levels:
 - Fine-grained level: user can decide to be recommended more according to a particular user feature (e.g., a 30-year-old wants to be recommended as a 50-year-old).
 - Coarse-grained level: user can decide some of his features to not affect the recommendation (e.g., a 30-year-old user does not want age to influence the recommended items).
- Item-feature controls also at two levels:
 - Fine-grained level: user can decide a particular item to be recommended more (e.g., user wants to be recommended more Romance movies)

- Coarse-grained level: user can decide to decrease the recommendations of the largest item category in user historical interactions.

Researchers also propose the Reranking model: a refined version of the UCI model above that uses a re-ranking policy adapted to the user choices.

The following are the three research questions of the paper.

- (1) How does UCI perform to adjust recommendations for alleviating filter bubbles via four kinds of user controls?
- (2) How do users can control the recommendations by the coefficients (i.e., α and β)?
- (3) How does the proposed counterfactual inference affect the recommendations?

2 WORKFLOW USED TO REPRODUCE THE EXPERIMENTS

In order to reproduce the experiment, we cloned the original repository and set up the environment so that the same versions of libraries are used. We don't want the different packages to have an influence on the results. We encountered quite a few warnings regarding the deprecated functions anyway.

When the environment was set up, we encountered some problems regarding the GPU drivers used by the authors. Since none of the team members has an NVIDIA driver we had to work around this problem and decided to try modifying the existing code to only use CPU. We used `tensor.cpu()` and `map_location=torch.device('cpu')` to execute the code using the memory accessible to the CPU. Since the sub-processes are executed in parallel when using GPU, we needed to insert `if __name__ == '__main__':` as a guard in the main module to avoid creating sub-processes recursively.

Another thing we had fix were some paths in the `main.py` file that were set up locally.

The input data was provided in the form of NumPy arrays. We didn't have the global picture of how the raw datasets looked like, but the data turned out to be sufficient for fitting and evaluating the recommender models.

The code raised an exception regarding some data types of the tensors. If we assume that the original code functioned well, then it might have to do with the changes that we introduced regarding the CPU. In order to fix it, we just needed to cast the type of some variable to `torch.LongTensor` in every one of the scripts where that definition was made.

There was a decision to be made on the experimental design: would we use the provided pre-trained models or train the models ourselves? Training the models would have arguably been the most correct way to reproduce the full experiment. If the paper proposes a model, we would like to see that we are able to train it ourselves on the input data and get similar evaluation results. A model without a well-tested and functional training step has no generalization power because cannot be trained on another data-set. However, we couldn't train all the models that were required for the experiments due to time-constraints. The switch from GPU to CPU pushed the training times to a range between 16 to 20 hours. And we had about 15 different models to be trained on 3 different data-sets. That was simply beyond the scope of this project.

We did, however, test that the code for the training step was executable and we successfully trained one model. With a little faith, one can be optimistic that all models could have been trained and that the fits were very similar to the pre-trained models.

Application of the PRIMAD model. Following the PRIMAD approach proposed in the article "Reproducibility of Data-Oriented Experiments in e-Science", we define which variables need to stay fixed, which instead are interchangeable, and finally which we have decided to change to test the reproducibility of the proposed experiment.

- Platform: by changing the platform, we can improve the independence and portability of an experiment. This is achieved by enabling the whole experiment to be run on CPU only. MacOS and UNIX distributions are now able to reproduce the experiment.
- Research Objective: the hypothesis of the experiment were not changed.
- Implementation: By rewriting the code to use only CPU, we lead to higher adoption in different communities. This is also an effect of the platform change.
- Method: the method proposed in the paper remained fixed.
- Author: all four students reproduced the experiments outcomes on different machines and operating systems.
- Data
 - Input Data: We researched new data from the data sets provided, but unluckily the data used in the experiment was provided in a non-standard format that did not allow us to test other data-sets easily.
 - Data parameters: Even though we could change some parameters for training the recommendation model, this step was not done as training required many hours (from 10 to 20) to run and the best models were already preselected by the authors.

3 RESULTS COMPARISON

After going through the workflow described above, our goal was to successfully reproduce 7 figures or tables from the original paper. This subset of chosen figures to reproduce were the ones that contained numerical results (and were not diagrams or illustrations). We will refer to them by their original name in the paper (e.g.: Table 5) even though it has no correspondence to the numbering of tables and figures in our work.

We just include some examples of the reproduced results in this report. The complete reproduced tables and plots can be found in the main repository of the reproducibility experiment.

Reproduction of Figure 2. The figures visualize distribution over top-3 item categories (2.a) and models will inherit the biased distributions. In 2.d and 2.e results on Amazon-Book and ML-1M datasets are presented.

When trying to reproduce these figures we encountered many problems. First of all, the data denoting the names of the categories was in Chinese which made the whole data analysis process much harder. Secondly, the data was pickled. The pickle module is not secure. It is possible to construct malicious pickle data which would execute arbitrary code during unpickling. Even though this method is not secure, we did try unpickling the data. The data comes in non standard formats and efforts should have been made to transform it which we thought were beyond the scope of this project.

Reproduction of Table 2,3,4. A major reproducibility drawback of this paper was that the baseline models for the FM and NFM engines were not provided. We will discuss the necessity of these models.

The user-feature coarse-grained controls and user-feature fine-grained controls are tested over the gender groups and the age groups of DIGIX-Video data set. We were able to reproduce the results achieved by the user-feature controls, however some baselines are missing as mentioned before.

The Reranking, C-UCI and F-UFI were implemented in different scripts and required four executions for each one of them (models FM and NFM, and two datasets). The three scripts had to be fixed as explained in the workflow description.

Reproduction of Figure 6. We were able to reproduce the complete figure. However, we include here 6(d) and 6(e) as an example. The source code for the plotting of the curves was not provided and was done in Excel.

Fig. 1. Reproduction of Figure 6 of the original paper. Reproduced results (left) vs original table (right).

Reproduction of Table 5. In this case, we were able to reproduce the table with precision. All of the entries in the table match the original entries. The difficulty, in this case, was that it was not clear how to specify the usage of Counterfactual Inference (CI) in a model. However, a comment in the source code gave us a hint: the hyper-parameter $\alpha < 1$ defines a model that uses CI, whereas $\alpha = 1$ does not use CI. The hyper-parameter β is free and set to its best setting.

4 CONFIRMATION OF THE FINDINGS

Regarding research question RQ_i, researchers claim the following RQ_{i,j} findings. On the bullet points, we comment on the validity of the conclusions and suggest better approaches. To study whether the findings of the authors can be confirmed or not, we will assume their results regardless of whether we were able to reproduce them or not.

RQ1.1: Using user-feature controls, UCI significantly alleviates the group segregation in filter bubbles achieving superior accuracy. Besides, the diversity also increases as compared to FM and NFM, which relieves the accuracy-diversity dilemma.

- Information that supports this is found on Table 2 and Table 3 of the original paper. Indeed, Recall and NCFG are superior while also improving coverage. But what does *significantly* mean in the conclusion? We claim that even though this is true for this particular train / test split, a statistical test should be performed on multiple executions to reduce the effect of statistical noise. For example, we propose a one-vs-one cross-validation approach to compare two models (we would have to do this for every pair of models). The results in a validation set for the two models would be naturally paired and we would use the paired t-test or Wilcoxon test for equal means. That would answer the question whether two models have provide superior accuracy or diversity.

RQ1.2: F-UCI achieves the best accuracy by following users' fine-grained item-feature controls.

- This is a general conclusion that follows from Table 4, where we can see that F-UCI (fine-grained) is actually an upper bound of C-UCI (coarse-grained). In this case, researchers have proven the inequality on both accuracies and diversities, on two data-sets. They also provide some possible reasons for the existence of this bound. In our opinion, the existence of such bound seems proven, even though one can always try a cross-validation approach and check if the bound is respected in each fold.

RQ2.1: α controls the influence of user-feature controls, where a larger α significantly alleviated the filter bubbles and enhances the diversity.

- This statement is based on Figure 6. We have that 6.a, 6.b, and 6.c are plots for the same data-set. Visual inspection clearly favours the claim but again, the expression *significantly* is used. In this particular case, we suggest that correlation measures could help picture better the (claimed) relationship between α and performance measures. For instance, we computed a -0.95 Pearson correlation coefficient for α and the Isolation coefficient, which highlights the quality of the linear relationship.

RQ2.2: UCI can mitigate filter bubbles and improve diversity without sacrificing accuracy or with less accuracy decline.

- This conclusion is made based on Figure 6(d) and 6(e). Telling from the plots, it's clearly true. However, it would have been more appropriate to check it on the three data-sets.

RQ2.3: Under item-feature controls, β is able to mitigate the domination of historical majority categories while improving accuracy.

- Our comment here is the same as in the previous point.

RQ3.1: Using counterfactual inference alleviates the filter bubbles, improves the diversity, and enhances the accuracy when α is small.

- This results are again based on Figure 6(d), 6(e) and Table 5, which were computed for only one data-set and we have already mentioned that the check on other data-set would make a stronger argument. As explained in some other comments, a cross-validation approach could have been used to compare the two models, especially for this case where we have a 1vs1 comparison (CI vs no-CI).

5 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVING REPRODUCIBILITY

Below are some ideas that would have helped our task of reproducing the paper:

- Data could be provided in a more transparent way. Ideally, a raw table would be provided (e.g.: .csv), and if necessary, the ETL to transform the raw data into the model input. In our case, we were given only some NumPy arrays that were difficult to understand and process.
- Code should use the most recent possible versions of libraries and languages. In our case, code was written in 2022 (according to commit history) and uses python3.7. But python 3.8 was already out in 2019, and 3.9 in 2020. They use pyTorch 1.4.0 when the latest version is 1.13. Some package managers like pip no longer provide the installers for such old versions.
- We recommend including baseline models in the source code. In this paper, five different baseline models are used to test the proposed improvements against their benchmark but their source code was not available. Instead, the paper that proposed the baseline models was referenced. Even though the referenced paper contains the source code for these models, we believe that for best reproducibility practices, these models should be imported to the current project.
- Code should be properly documented (comments are not enough). It is always good practice to add documentation docstrings in (important) functions, classes and methods that can then be compiled into a documentation pdf for the project. This was not available in the code of the paper and the comments were sometimes not enough to understand the workflow of a process. We also recommend not including key information for reproducibility as a comment in the code but adding it in the Readme file. For instance, the best hyper-parameter configurations for each model were comments in the middle of the script.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND LESSONS LEARNED

During the reproduction of this paper, we gained insight into the challenges of reproducibility. This made us realize the importance of proper standardization and documentation of components,

procedures, and workflows in the experiments. We can say that the authors of the paper did a good job at documenting their work but there were parts they missed including, as mentioned above. We managed to reproduce the majority of their experiments and our results match the ones reported in the paper. Regarding the findings claimed by the researchers, we agree on the fact that the conclusions are logical but we suggest ways to improve the conclusions in a statistical sense. We also included recommendations for improving reproducibility which we believe would make the whole process even smoother. We pushed to the repository all our bug fixes and included additional documentation that could have helped us with the idea to help future researchers or students willing to reproduce the experiment.